

Studies in Cyclo-octane series : Part V. Synthesis of 3 : 4-hexamethylene-arylsubstituted-2-quinolones

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Condensation of ethyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate with a number of primary aromatic amines is carried out at 180-190° when the respective anilides are obtained. Some of these are easily cyclised either with sulphuric acid or poly-phosphoric acid to give 3:4-hexamethylene-arylsubstituted-2-quinolones.

Cyclic β -keto esters react with primary aromatic amines and heterocyclic bases to give anils, anilides or amides depending upon the reaction temperature¹⁻⁸. The anilides on cyclisation furnish α -quinindones or tetra-hydrophenanthridones according to the nature of the cyclic β -keto ester.

Brown, Carver and Hollingsworth (*loc. cit.*) report that the anilides (I ; n=3) obtained by condensing a large number of primary arylamines with ethyl cyclopentan-1-one-2-carboxylate could be cyclised to yield 2 : 3-dihydro- α -quinindones (II ; n=3). These workers further observed that anilides having a nitro, methoxyl, hydroxyl, phenyl or carboxylic acid group in the aromatic ring of the base could not be cyclised.

Condensation of ethyl cycloheptan-1-one-2-carboxylate with aniline⁹ gave the anilide (I ; n=5) which on cyclisation yielded 3 : 4-cyclohepteno-2-quinolone (II ; n=5).

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Bhargava and Saharia (unpublished work) have extended the work by condensing the above keto ester with a large number of bases both at room temperature and at 180-190° and the products so obtained have been cyclised to form the substituted 4- or 2-quinolones.

The work reported in this paper describes the condensation of ethyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate with a large number of primary aromatic amines which was taken up with the idea of studying the effect of the eight membered ring on this and subsequent reactions. Equimolecular proportions of the above keto ester and the base were heated at 180-190° for three minutes and the anilides (I : $n=6$) so obtained were crystallised from dilute ethanol ; these products gave a violet colouration with aqueous ferric chloride. Only five of these (I ; $n=6$: $\text{Ar}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, *o*-, *m* & *p*- $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}_3$ and $\beta\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7$) could be cyclised to form 3 : 4-hexamethylene-2-quinolone and 3 : 4-hexamethylene-arylsubstituted-2-quinolones, the first four with sulphuric acid and the fifth with polyphosphoric acid. These were crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

The anilides which had bromine, chlorine, methoxyl, nitro or two methyl groups in 2 : 5-positions in the aromatic ring failed to cyclise with sulphuric acid or polyphosphoric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of cyclo-octan-1-one-2-anilides :—A mixture of ethyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate (0.005 mol) and the base (0.005 mol) was heated for three minutes in an oil bath at 180-190° ; the reaction product on cooling was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution extracted thrice with aqueous sodium hydroxide (2%). The combined alkaline extracts on acidification with glacial acetic acid deposited the anilide as a solid, which was crystallised from dilute ethanol. The alcoholic solutions of the anilides gave a distinct colouration with aqueous ferric chloride.

Synthesis of 3 : 4-hexamethylene-2-quinolones :

(A) Cyclo-octan-1-one-2-anilide (0.5 g) was added in small lots to ice-cold concentrated sulphuric acid (5 ml) and the mixture, after heating in a boiling water bath for 15 minutes, was poured over crushed ice when a colourless solid separated out. This was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid and did not give any colouration with aqueous ferric chloride.

(B) To polyphosphoric acid prepared by dissolving phosphorus pentoxide (15 g) in ortho phosphoric acid (10 ml) contained in a R. B. flask fitted with a guard tube, was added the anilide (0.5 g) and the contents heated on a boiling water bath for 30 minutes with occasional shaking. The cold yellow reaction product was decomposed by adding ice-cold water, when a crude colourless solid separated. It was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid and did not give any colouration with aqueous ferric chloride.

TABLE I

Cyclo-octan-1-one-2-anilides.

S. No.	Name of the Anilide	Crystalline appearance	M. P. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	Found (%)		Requires (%)	
						C	H	C	H
(Cyclo-octan-1-one-)									
1.	„ -2-anilide	Colourless needles.	103	55.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	73.4	7.5	73.4	7.8
2.	„ -2- <i>p</i> -toluidide	„	117	58.5	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	73.9	8.2	74.1	8.2
3.	„ -2- <i>m</i> -toluidide	Colourless plates.	84	56.8	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	74.2	8.4	74.1	8.2
4.	„ -2- <i>o</i> -toluidide	„	111	54.2	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	74.0	8.2	74.1	8.2
5.	„ -2-naphthylidide.	Colourless needles.	129	68	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	77.3	7.0	77.3	7.2
6.	„ - <i>p</i> -bromoanilide	„	144	70.5	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ NBr	55.3	5.4	55.5	5.5
7.	„ - <i>p</i> -chloroanilide	„	138	55.5	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ NCl	64.2	6.5	64.4	6.4
8.	„ - <i>m</i> -anisidide	Colourless plates.	110	60	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	70.0	7.5	69.8	7.6
9.	„ - <i>m</i> -nitroanilide.	Colourless needles.	110	46	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂	62.0	6.4	62.1	6.2
10.	„ 2:5-xylidide	„	124	64	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	74.5	8.3	74.7	8.4

TABLE II

3 : 4-Hexamethylene-arylsubstituted-2-quinolones.

S. No.	Name of the compound	Crystalline appearance	M. P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found (%)		Requires (%)	
						C	H	C	H
1.	3:4-Hexamethylene -2-quinolone.	Colourless cubes.	262	75.5	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON	79.5	7.6	79.3	7.5
2.	„ „ -6-methyl -2-quinolone.	„	268	73.4	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	79.5	7.9	79.6	7.9
3.	„ „ -7-methyl -2-quinolone.	Colourless needles.	258	65.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	72.4	7.8	79.6	7.9
4.	„ „ -8-Methyl -2-quinolone.	Colourless plates.	223-4	65.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	79.5	8.1	79.6	7.9
5.	„ „ -5:6-benz- -2-quinolone.	Colourless cubes.	277-8	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON	82.2	6.6	82.3	6.9

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